

Numerical Analysis of Combustion Process in the Dual Fuel Internal Combustion Engine

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Abstract

Fully flexible dual fuel (DF) internal combustion (IC) engines, that can burn diesel and gas simultaneously, have become established among heavy-duty engines as they contribute significantly to lower the environmental impact of the transport sector. In order to gain better understanding of the DF combustion process and establish an effective design methodology for DFIC engines, high fidelity computational fluid dynamics (CFD) simulation tools are needed. The DF strategy poses new challenges for numerical modelling of the combustion process since all combustion regimes have to be modelled simultaneously. Furthermore, DF engines exhibit higher cycle-to-cycle variations (CCV) compared to the pure diesel engines. This issue can be addressed by employing large eddy simulation coupled with appropriate DF detailed chemistry mechanism. However, such an approach is computationally too expensive for today's industry-related engine calculations. On the other hand,

Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) based simulations coupled with combustion models lack the fidelity to accurately capture underlying flow physics. This work couples the Partially-Averaged Navier-Stokes (PANS) turbulence method with flamelet-generated manifold (FGM) tabulated chemistry approach for combustion modelling with the objective to provide an optimum between accuracy and computational cost. The PANS method is a scale resolving turbulence model which seamlessly vary from RANS to direct numerical simulation (DNS) depending upon the prescribed cut-off length. Two reaction mechanisms optimized for DF combustion process, using n-heptane and a mixture of methane/propane, were tested in order to find the most suitable mechanism for the generation of the FGM table. The feasibility of the methodology and ability to capture CCV is tested by simulating three different operating points of DF single cylinder research engine. The numerically obtained results are compared with the available experimental data.

Introduction

In 2021, pandemic restrictions were revoked, and transport activities increased again after the unprecedented decline in 2020. According to [1], this has led to an 8% jump in CO₂ emissions from transport sector compared to the previous year. In addition, relevant forecasts anticipate growth in transport demand associated with the expansion of urbanization and population growth in developing and emerging economies [2]. To achieve Paris Agreement's goal of limiting global warming to less than 1.5 degrees Celsius compared to pre-industrial levels, a broad set of policies and measures has to be implemented. Such as the rapid electrification of road vehicles and the introduction of low-carbon or low-emission fuels. Adoption of low-carbon fuels concerns especially marine sector and non-exhaustive list of heavy-duty engines, for which no electrification strategy is in place. One of the promising concepts for marine, transportation and even

power generation applications that has emerged in recent years, is a so-called dual-fuel (DF) internal combustion (IC) engine. It has been shown that DF operational mode is associated with exhaust emissions that are less detrimental to the environment from the other forms IC engines [3]. Therefore, it represents a practical and imminent solution on the pathway towards climate neutral world by mid-century.

This paper focuses on a diesel-ignited gas engine which is operated by burning a premixed high-octane fuel/air mixture ignited with a small amount of directly injected high-cetane fuel. Diesel fuel is employed as ignition agent, while for the gaseous fuel natural gas was utilized. This results in lower NO_x and soot emissions compared to the monovalent diesel engines. Due to the higher ignition energy of diesel fuel compared to a spark plug, it is possible to ignite different natural gas compositions. Thus, the fuel flexibility of the DF engine is higher compared to a pure gas engine. On the other

hand, NO_x emission is higher compared to the gas engine [4]. Moreover, the efficiency of DF engine is lower compared to the pure gas engine [4]. Disadvantages of DF engines are discussed in [5]. However, utilization of such concept can satisfy strict emission legislation. Moreover, DF engines comply with the Tier 3 limit of the International Marine Organization (IMO) [6]. Thus, they are subject of active research, and effective design of DFIC engines and fuel injection equipment for DFIC engine represents a key priority.

One of the well-established approaches for design of IC engines is utilization of computational fluid dynamics (CFD) tools. For large engines, accurate prediction with simulation tools is even more important due to the reduced number of prototypes in the development and test phases [7]. The combustion processes involve many closely coupled physical and chemical phenomena, hence, performing the proper modelling of cylinder events is a complex task. Moreover, in DF operational mode all the combustion regimes i.e., autoignition, diffusion combustion and premixed flame propagation occur simultaneously. Thus, numerical modelling of DF combustion is even more challenging. The process can be accurately described by employing detailed chemical mechanism which has to cover all the necessary reactions for both fuels. Such mechanism can involve several thousands of chemical species and elementary reactions. Thus, significant computational power is required, even if the turbulent flow field is fully modelled, e.g., Reynolds Averaged Navier Stokes equations are solved. In [8], a detailed chemistry mechanism was used for DF combustion study for a heavy-duty engine. To speed-up the calculation time, Liu et al. [9] developed a thermodynamic multizone model incorporating a detailed chemistry mechanism for DF combustion. Hockett et al. [10], as well as Schuh et al. [11] constructed a reduced DF chemical kinetic mechanism. However, even with reduced chemistry, engine simulation of industrial interest is limited to the RANS framework due to long computational time. This has led to the development of combustion models capable of providing a faster result while preserving high predictive accuracy, such as tabulated chemistry approaches. Focus of this paper is the Flamelet Generated Manifold (FGM) combustion model which is a powerful tool for engineering applications. The FGM model ensures affordable computational time and accuracy in the following way: a chemical mechanism with desired degree of detail is used to pre-compute combustion chemistry, relevant data is stored in a look-up table as a function of few controlling variables, and during the numerical simulation a minimal number of transport equations are solved while thermochemical data is interpolated from the table. An overview of the FGM combustion modelling approach can be found in [12]. The FGM model has proven to be able to accurately simulate the combustion processes in a diesel engine [13] as well as in a gasoline engine [14]. A methodology for handling multiple fuels within the FGM tabulated chemistry approach model can be found in [15].

It has been reported that a diesel ignited gas engine exhibits higher cycle to cycle variations (CCV) compared to the conventional diesel engine [16]. Possible sources of CCVs in DF engines are various, such as, non-optimal injector performance (variability in injected pilot fuel mass, start and duration of injection, nozzle hole-to-hole variability etc.),

stochastic nature of pre-mixing of air and natural gas and initial and boundary conditions (temperature, pressure and residual gases) [17]. Higher CCVs are generally understood to lead to lower engine efficiency and higher emission levels. Therefore, it is important to identify and understand critical parameters leading to CCVs in DF operational mode. CCVs have been extensively investigated, both experimentally and numerically, in gas [18] and diesel engines [19]. However, there are only few studies on CCVs of the DF engine. To predict engine CCV and all related flow phenomena with a CFD simulation, Large Eddy Simulation (LES) method for turbulence modelling should be employed. Although LES method resolves all relevant flow structures and offers more thorough elucidation of flame topology, today's industry related engine simulations are based upon RANS method which can only provide cycle-averaged results i.e., it cannot be used to investigate CCV. The reason to utilize RANS over LES, is that LES method is associated with increased computational cost since it requires very fine meshes, roughly one order of magnitude larger than RANS. Moreover, by taking multiple cycle simulation into account it becomes clear that LES is impractical for industrial everyday use. Therefore, it becomes a necessity to adopt numerical models capable of providing a balance between accuracy and computational cost, namely hybrid RANS/LES models. One of the hybrid methods that has shown promise in recent years is Partially Averaged Navier Stokes (PANS) method. PANS is a scale resolving method envisioned to capture only important large-scale fluctuations while the remainder of flow scales is modelled. Thus, it provides improved results over RANS method with significantly lower computational cost than LES calculation. Successful application of PANS method is demonstrated in variety of applications. There are several variants of PANS derived up to date, in this work a PANS model based on the k-zeta-f model derived by Basara et al. [20] is utilized.

The aim of this study is to investigate and propose an optimal numerical method for calculating DF combustion process with respect to the accuracy and computational cost. For that purpose, two different approaches to calculate combustion process using 3D CFD tool are employed, namely the General Gas Phase Reaction (GGPR) approach in which a transport equation for every species in the reaction mechanism is solved and FGM tabulated chemistry model. Both, GGPR and FGM are coupled with RANS, PANS and LES turbulence models. Engine simulation employing GGPR and based on the LES framework should provide much more detailed insight into the combustion process compared to the results obtained by RANS simulation coupled with a combustion model. However, this approach is not feasible for industrial applications. Therefore, in this study it is proposed to employ the FGM model for chemistry and PANS method to model turbulent flow, as a methodology that can provide optimum between accuracy and computational cost. Two reaction mechanism optimized for DF combustion with different degree of detail were tested and the most suitable one is employed to generated FGM table. Three computational meshes with different resolution were employed to demonstrate differences with respect to the computational time and accuracy when utilizing different turbulence modelling approaches. The PANS framework is only partially stated in

this paper, cf. [21] for detailed information on mathematical background. The feasibility of the FGM PANS methodology to provide accurate and computationally more affordable results compared to the GGPR simulation coupled with LES approach for turbulence modelling in DF configuration was investigated. Numerical investigation of CCV utilizing FGM PANS methodology was performed. The numerically obtained results are validated against engine measurements conducted on a single cylinder diesel ignited gas engine at the Large Engines Competence Center in Graz.

Numerical Method

Partially Averaged Navier Stokes Turbulence Model

The PANS method is a scale resolving turbulence model which gradually changes from RANS to direct numerical solution of the Navier-Stokes equations as the model resolution parameter reduces from unity to zero. The model is based on a so called “partial averaging” concept, in which only a part of the fluctuating scales is filtered. The PANS equations are written in terms of the partially averaged or filtered pressure and velocity field:

$$\frac{\partial U_i}{\partial t} + U_j \frac{\partial U_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial \tau(V_i, V_j)}{\partial x_j} = -\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial p}{\partial x_i} + \nu \frac{\partial^2 U_i}{\partial x_j \partial x_j} \quad (1)$$

Where V_i represents instantaneous velocity field decomposed into the partially filtered component U_i and sub-filtered or unresolved component u_i . The Boussinesq assumption is utilized to model unknown Reynolds stresses in Eq. 1 as follows:

$$\tau(V_i, V_j) = -\nu_u \left(\frac{\partial U_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial U_j}{\partial x_i} \right) + \frac{2}{3} k_u \delta_{ij} \quad (2)$$

Where ν_u is an eddy viscosity of unresolved scales and set as:

$$\nu_u = C_\mu \frac{k_u^2}{\varepsilon_u} \quad (3)$$

To close the system of equations given above, transport equations for the unresolved kinetic energy k_u and unresolved dissipation ε_u are required. The PANS method implemented in AVL FIRE™ is based on the work of Basara et al. [20]. This model variant is derived from the four equation RANS model, the $k-\varepsilon-\zeta$ -f model. Accurate near wall modelling is important for many industrial applications. Since the $k-\varepsilon-\zeta$ -f model has proven excellent near-wall characteristic it serves as a good basis for an enhancement of PANS performance. In addition to the equations for kinetic energy and dissipation this model solves an equation for wall-normal unresolved velocity scale ratio $\zeta = \nu^2 / k$ and elliptic relaxation function, which is parameter closely related to pressure strain redistribution term. A detailed description of the $k-\varepsilon-\zeta$ -f model can be found in [22]. In the derivation of the abovementioned transport equations two resolution parameters have been introduced,

namely unresolved-to-total ratio of kinetic energy f_k and dissipation f_ε which define the range of resolved scales of the turbulent flow:

$$f_k = \frac{k_u}{k} \quad f_\varepsilon = \frac{\varepsilon_u}{\varepsilon} \quad (4)$$

If the resolution parameters go to zero, the PANS equations reduce to the Navier-Stokes equations. If they are equal to unity, equations of the parent RANS model are recovered. These values are needed as an input at the beginning of the simulation (even for every time step). However, they can be determined only at the end of the calculation. Therefore, Basara et al. [23] proposed a dynamic update of the f_k parameter as a function of grid spacing based on the work presented in [24]:

$$f_k \geq \frac{1}{\sqrt{C_\mu}} \left(\frac{\Delta}{\Lambda} \right)^{2/3} > \frac{k_u}{k} \quad (5)$$

Where Δ is the grid cell dimension and Λ is an integral length scale ($\Lambda = k^{3/2} / \varepsilon$). Note in order to determine the integral length scale total kinetic energy is needed ($k = k_u + k_r$) and this can be calculated only after the resolved field is obtained. A dynamic f_k changes in every cell at the end of the time step, and then it is used as input for the next time step [25]. Eq. 5 is inequality because it must be ensured that f_k imposed on the calculation is supported by the mesh. This approach has shown to perform good in variety of cases which include static meshes. However, for complex unsteady flows with moving boundaries this approach is impractical, because it involves expensive averaging of resolved flow field. Therefore, Basara et al. [21] further enhanced the PANS $k-\varepsilon-\zeta$ -f model by developing an additional equation to determine resolved turbulent kinetic energy, called scale supplying variable (SSV). The derivation of this equation is presented in the original paper. Both, resolved and unresolved kinetic energy are continuously calculated, hence in-situ specification of f_k depending on the flow and computational mesh is enabled. Such approach provides efficient PANS calculations of applications with moving geometries and transient boundaries. Therefore, it is used here for the calculation of combustion process in DF engine.

General Gas Phase Reaction

The GGPR approach for 3D CFD simulation of combustion processes uses various chemical mechanisms that involve large number of chemical species and elementary reactions. Since for every species in the mechanism a transport equation has to be solved higher modeling accuracy can be achieved but at a higher computational cost. Diesel fuel is a complex mixture that can consists of several thousand of hydrocarbon compounds with carbon number from 6 to 28 [11]. Hence, considering detailed chemistry would lead to an enormous computational demand. For that reason, it is common to utilize a substitute fuel that can mimic overall combustion behavior of diesel. In this study, n-heptane was used as a surrogate for diesel. In addition, it is necessary to define a surrogate for natural gas. To retain a correct methane number

of natural gas, a mixture of methane and propane was employed as a surrogate fuel [26].

Ignition delay time of different fuel mixtures is strongly influenced by its chemical kinetics. Premixing gaseous fuel with the air in the cylinder changes mixture formation and the combustion characteristics of the pilot diesel fuel. It has been proven, both experimentally [27] and numerically [28] that methane strongly prolongs the ignition delay time of n-heptane. The behavior of ignition delay time for different fuel blends of n-heptane and methane is presented in [4]. For the correct description of autoignition of DF mixture it is crucial to employ an appropriate chemical mechanism. Both fuels, in this case diesel and natural gas, have to be represented in the reaction chemistry. In the work of [29], LLNL n-heptane and NUI natural gas [30] mechanisms were merged and evaluated. The final mechanism considers 3037 elementary reaction and 695 species, and it was employed in this study for simulation of combustion process in DF engine. The mechanism is denoted as detailed DF mechanism throughout this work. In addition, a more compact mechanism, namely TU Wien DF mechanism [11] which consist of 344 reactions and 75 species was tested.

In Figure 1 pressure traces obtained with detailed and TU Wien mechanism for one engine operating point are compared to the measurement, represented with a star and circle, respectively. In addition, the same simulation is performed employing mechanism which considers only diesel fuel reactions, namely LLNL n-heptane. Both DF mechanisms predicted measured pressure trace accurately with respect to the start of the combustion and the peak pressure value. The pressure trace obtained with the LLNL n-heptane mechanism predicted start of the combustion earlier compared to the measurement. A comparison of an ignition delay time obtained from 0D simulation form three tested mechanisms is shown in Figure 2. It is visible that both DF mechanisms are characterized with longer ignition delay time compared to pure n-heptane mechanism. This can be seen as confirmation that methane prolonged ignition delay time of diesel fuel. Since both DF mechanism exhibited similar results, to reduce

FIGURE 1 Predicted pressure employing LLNL n-heptane (box), Detailed DF (star) and TU Wien DF (circle) mechanisms in comparison to measurement

FIGURE 2 Comparison of ignition delay time for LLNL n-heptane (box), Detailed DF (star) and TU Wien DF (circle) mechanisms

computational time in all further simulations the TU Wien mechanism was employed.

Flamelet Generated Manifold

The FGM combustion model is a powerful tool for CFD simulation of IC engines of industrial interest since it enables significant speed up in computational time while utilizing detailed chemistry. The model is developed by Colin and Van Oijen [12] as a combination of flamelet and manifold approaches. The basic idea is that a turbulent multidimensional flame can be decomposed into laminar, locally one-dimensional flames embedded into the flow field called flamelets. In addition, it is assumed that chemical scales are one order of magnitude smaller than the turbulent scales. These assumptions allow decoupled flow computation from the flame structure calculation. Which means that the combustion chemistry is pre-computed and thermochemical data of the flamelets are stored in a look-up table and interpolated during CFD simulation. In the present work, the FGM look-up tables are generated with the AVL TABKINTM table generation tool based on the homogeneous reactor chemistry calculations. The tables have up to 10 dimensions: pressure, fresh gas temperature, mixture fraction, mixture fraction variance, 1st progress variable, 2nd progress variable, 2nd progress variable variance, EGR and fuel ratio in case of dual fuel simulation. A second progress variable is implemented to track slow chemistry process, for example nitrogen oxidation. To generate the table, a chemical mechanism with any degree of detail can be used. Thus, no accuracy is lost due to reduced chemistry. More details about table generation can be found in [31]. The data is stored in the table as a function of two independent variables, namely mixture fraction (Z) and progress variable (PV). For the purpose of this work, a Synthetic Thermodynamics (ST) approach available in AVL FIRETM for TABKINTM FGM simulation is employed. Detailed description of this approach can be found in [15]. When utilizing the ST approach, during the CFD simulation of the DF combustion process 7 artificial

species are transported. In addition, transport equations for mixture fraction, progress variable and their variances are solved. Mixture fraction and progress variable are conserved scalars describing the mixing process between air and fuel and advancement of the combustion process from the unburnt to burnt gas, respectively. For the DF combustion process, two scalars are needed to describe mixing process between oxidizer and fuel, one for the premixed fuel and second for the pilot fuel. The general transport equation for the control variables and their variances is written as:

$$\frac{\partial \bar{\rho} \varphi}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \bar{\rho} \tilde{u}_i \tilde{\varphi}}{\partial x_i} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left(\bar{\rho} (D + D_T) \frac{\partial \tilde{\varphi}}{\partial x_i} \right) + \bar{\omega}_{\varphi} \quad (6)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{\partial \bar{\rho} \tilde{\varphi}_{\text{var}}}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \bar{\rho} \tilde{u}_i \tilde{\varphi}_{\text{var}}}{\partial x_i} \\ &= \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left(\bar{\rho} (D + D_T) \frac{\partial \tilde{\varphi}_{\text{var}}}{\partial x_i} \right) \\ &+ 2 \bar{\rho} D_T \left(\frac{\partial \tilde{\varphi}_{\text{var}}}{\partial x_i} \right)^2 - \bar{\rho} \tilde{\chi}_{\varphi} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Where φ can represent Z or PV. D and D_T are laminar and turbulent diffusion coefficient of the fuel species. $\bar{\omega}_{\varphi}$ is a source term coming from chemistry and spray, for PV and Z respectively. $\tilde{\chi}_{\varphi}$ is scalar dissipation defined as follows:

$$\tilde{\chi}_{\varphi} = 2 \frac{\varepsilon}{k} \tilde{\varphi}_{\text{var}} \quad (8)$$

In case of PANS, the effect of the unresolved part of turbulent kinetic energy and dissipation on scalar dissipation is considered. Additionally, to account for the turbulence effects on combustion process the β -Presumed Probability Density Function (PPDF) approach is adopted.

To establish fair comparison of the results obtained with the FGM model to the GGPR results, the FGM table was generated with the same mechanism used in the GGPR simulation, namely TU Wien. The table is discretized in the way that higher refinement is performed for the most reactive conditions with the respect to the n-heptane autoignition time. [Figures 3, 4](#) and [5](#) visualize the output of the

FIGURE 3 Progress variable source term as function of mixture fraction and the progress variable for fuel ratio equal to zero

FIGURE 4 Progress variable source term as function of mixture fraction and the progress variable for fuel ratio equal to 0.8

FIGURE 5 Progress variable source term as function of mixture fraction and the progress variable for fuel ratio equal to unity

0D PSR simulation for fuel ratio 0 (n-heptane), 0.8 (80% of methane in dual fuel mixture) and 1 (pure methane) at temperature of 870 K and pressure of 45 bar. The progress variable source term is mapped onto the predefined progress variable and mixture fraction grid. When the fuel ratio is equal zero, the table returns the same source value as for the pure n-heptane case. In case of 80% methane content in DF mixture the values are closer to the pure methane. The progress variable term has its maximum at the stoichiometric mixture fraction.

Spray Modelling

The fuel injection is a necessary process used to disperse liquid fuel in a broader area of combustion chamber and to increase the surface needed for the more intensive evaporation process. In IC engines, the spray is produced by introducing liquid fuel into the combustion chamber through a nozzle under high injection pressure. Accurate modelling of diesel injection process is important in order to understand the spray formation, its interaction with the surrounding air in the cylinder and the location where diesel will ignite to achieve more efficient and complete combustion followed by lower pollutant emissions.

In the present study a spray model based on the Lagrangian Discrete Droplet Method is employed. The method consists of a combination of standard Eulerian conservation equations for the continuous gaseous phase and Lagrangian tracking of droplet parcels for the transport of the dispersed phase. The parcel represents a group of droplets similar in size and physical properties. These equations are coupled by mass, momentum, energy and turbulence exchange between the liquid and the gas phase. To account for primary and secondary atomization, evaporation, wall interaction and turbulent dispersion a set of spray sub-models is employed. The sub-models include the WAVE beak-up model, the Dukowicz evaporation model and the Walljet wall interaction model based on the spray/wall impingement model of Naber and Reitz [32]. The effect of turbulence on spray particles in general can't be resolved in detail, hence, it is accounted for by the turbulent dispersion model. The PANS turbulent dispersion effects on the spray are considered by interaction between resolved flow scales and the spray droplets.

As stated before, diesel fuel was utilized to provide required ignition energy and start the flame propagation through the lean mixture of natural gas and air. A very small amount of diesel fuel, even 1% diesel fraction is sufficient to start the combustion process. The injector in dual-fuel configuration operates in the so-called ballistic mode, meaning it has to be capable of handling short injection duration under high pressure. Therefore, the behavior of the diesel injection is different compared to the normal diesel engine and the numerical simulation has to be treated accordingly [4]. The present work doesn't consider modifications of the spray models. Malin et al. [33] modified and calibrated already existing models for the adapted injector so that the model can consider the ballistic region of the needle lift. These modifications and optimized parameters are adapted in this work. In the [33] vapor and penetration lengths of the simulation are compared to the measurements.

Engine and Operating Conditions

Measurements used for validation of proposed methodology were carried out at the Large Engines Competence Center GmbH in Graz. For the experimental investigation a large high speed four stroke single cylinder diesel-gas dual fuel research engine was utilized. The engine has a displacement of approximately 6 cubic decimeters. The truck sized injector with the four symmetrically arranged nozzle holes was positioned in the center of the cylinder head. Diesel fuel for the pilot injection was supplied by the common rail system with up to 1600 bar rail pressure. Exhaust gas recirculation (EGR) was not considered in the presented measurements. Further information on the engine specification and experimental setup can be found in [5]. For the present study three representative operating conditions are selected which differ in the injection timing of the pilot diesel fuel. Injection timing was varied -10°CA and $+10^{\circ}\text{CA}$ from the nominal operating point. In the work of Redtenbacher et al. [5] it has been found that

varying injection timing at the small diesel fractions, such as 1%, leads to the significantly different combustion characteristics. Therefore, these three operational points serve as a robust foundation for the investigation of the dual-fuel combustion process, and consequently, they were simulated in this study.

Numerical Procedure

In the present study, the 3D-CFD simulations were performed using the commercial CFD code AVL FIRE™ which is based on the fully conservative finite volume approach. The method is fully implicit and allows the use of unstructured moving grids composed of arbitrary polyhedral. All the dependent variables are evaluated at the center of the control volume. The convection is solved by a variety of differencing schemes. For the turbulence and energy transport equation, first order upwind differencing was applied, while for the continuity equation, central differencing was employed. The momentum equation was discretized using the MINMOD relaxed scheme. The overall solution procedure is iterative, and it is based on the SIMPLE/PISO method which is a combination of SIMPLE algorithm and PISO corrections. For the temporal discretization a first order accurate Euler implicit scheme was adopted. Three computational meshes with different resolution levels were generated using AVL FIRE™ ESE Diesel mesh generator. The generated computational domain is only fourth of the combustion chamber since the diesel injector has four symmetrically arranged nozzle holes. Only the high-pressure phase was simulated. Characteristic data for each mesh is given in the Table 1 and the coarse computational meshes is shown in Figure 6. Comparison between mean in-cylinder

TABLE 1 Computational domain characterization

Mesh resolution	No. of cells at TDC	No. of cells at BDC	Average cell size
Coarse	28 308	164 577	2 mm
Medium	94 290	525 525	1 mm
Fine	389 125	2 314 750	0.5 mm

FIGURE 6 Coarse computational mesh used in simulation

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FIGURE 7 Mesh dependency test for RANS computation

pressure curves as predicted by RANS simulation on coarse, medium and fine mesh is shown in Figure 7. To obtain better visibility of the results, only the period from the start of the fuel injection to 770 °CA is shown. Mesh dependency results exhibit similar values for all computational meshes. Therefore, it can be concluded that RANS computation is grid-independent. For the LES simulation a sub-grid model based on coherent structure function [34] was adopted.

Results

For each experimentally investigated operating point, only averaged pressure evolution traces were provided to validate numerical results. Due to confidentiality reasons, the piston geometry is not shown. Additionally, scales are removed from the pressure plots. To provide relative comparison between operating points, scales and range in the plots are kept constant or slightly magnified. In the present work, three computational meshes were tested. The resolution parameter f_k obtained from PANS calculation on the coarse, medium and fine mesh is shown in Figure 8. The coarse mesh has high values of f_k which indicates that this is a typical mesh resolution for RANS calculations and employing PANS on this mesh wouldn't provide significantly different results than those from RANS simulation. As expected in case of medium mesh f_k values are smaller compared to the coarse mesh, while the distribution is similar. However, according to the Pope's principle [35] of 20% modelled kinetic energy this mesh is not appropriate for LES calculation. Therefore, another mesh with finer resolution purported for LES simulation is generated. Looking at the f_k distribution on the fine mesh it can be concluded that large portion of the spray will not be resolved by the mesh. In addition, it should be noted that f_k values are much lower than 1 in the central part of the cylinder and equal to one in the vicinity of the wall. For industrial applications it is not affordable to have fine numerical grids needed for wall-resolved LES calculation. Therefore, the PANS approach used in conjunction with the wall treatment that combines integration up to the wall with wall functions is ideally suited to improve accuracy of the calculations on the meshes such

FIGURE 8 The resolution parameter f_k as predicted by PANS on a) coarse mesh b) medium mesh and c) fine mesh

as the fine mesh used in this work. Instantaneous results from the PANS calculation on a medium mesh are shown in the Figure 9. The resolution parameter obtained by using $k = k_{it} + k_{ssv}$ (upper left), the total turbulent kinetic energy (upper right), the unresolved or SGS turbulent kinetic energy (lower left) and the scale supplying energy (lower right) are shown. Comparing the results, it can be observed that maximum of unresolved energy is in the region where f_k is equal to one. On the contrary, maximum of the resolved energy is in the middle of the cylinder where the f_k values are lower. SSV minimum is in the spray region and near to the wall. The total turbulent kinetic energy is sum of SGS and SSV turbulent kinetic energy.

As a first step, the early injection operating point of the DF engine has been calculated employing the GGPR approach with TU Wien DF mechanism. Secondly, the same operating point is calculated utilizing FGM tabulated chemistry

FIGURE 9 Resolution parameter f_k (upper left), total (upper right), unresolved (lower left) and modelled resolved (lower right) turbulent kinetic energy as predicted by PANS on the medium mesh

FIGURE 10 Pressure traces obtained from the GGPR (box) and FGM (star) simulation in comparison to the measurement for the early injection engine operating point

FIGURE 11 Pressure traces obtained from the LES (star) and PANS (full line) simulation in comparison to the measurement for the early injection engine operating point

methodology where the FGM table is generated from the same chemistry mechanism. Both calculations are performed on the fine mesh adopting the LES CSM [34] approach for turbulence modelling. Figure 10 shows the pressure traces obtained from GGPR simulation (marked with the box) and FGM simulation (marked with star) in comparison to the average pressure trace from the experiment. Both simulation results are in good agreement with the measurement.

In terms of computational effort, the present study was executed on a cluster consisting of 64 compute nodes, each with two Intel® Xeon® Gold 6154 3.00GHz processors containing 18 cores. Prior to the simulation, the FGM table had to be generated. Generation time for the table used in this study is 1h and 40 min. With respect to the solver turnaround times, the GGPR simulation took 52h and 30 min, while the result of FGM simulation was available after 26h and 48min, see Table 4. It is evident that reduction in computational time for the same accuracy in this case is substantial.

Next, the same engine operating point is calculated utilizing medium mesh resolution employing the same FGM tabulated chemistry coupled with PANS approach for turbulence modelling. Figure 11 shows the outcome of the simulation in comparison to both, measurement and previously shown FGM simulation coupled with LES on the fine mesh. The pressure trace obtained on the medium mesh utilizing PANS approach slightly underpredicts measured peak pressure value. However, this is only first cycle of PANS simulation compared to the averaged experimentally measured pressure. Solver turnaround time for the PANS simulation on the medium mesh is 5h and 24 min.

Predicted velocity, temperature and fuel ratio field during the injection phase obtained from the RANS (on the left) and PANS (on the right) simulation on the same medium mesh are shown in Figure 12. As can be seen from the obtained results, the prediction by RANS doesn't show much small-scale structures. Contrary to RANS, PANS results show much more wrinkles due to resolving portion of fluctuating flow scales. The fuel ratio field clearly identifies premixed,

FIGURE 12 Velocity, temperature and fuel ratio fields as obtained by RANS (on the left) and PANS (on the right) simulation for the injection phase

non-premixed and partially premixed regions in the domain. Partially premixed clusters occur in the region of evaporated diesel fuel since the fuel ratio scalar considers only the gaseous phase of the mixture fraction.

CFD simulations based on RANS turbulence models are widely used for design and optimization of IC engines because of their efficiency and reliability. However, this approach cannot capture unsteady features of a turbulent combustion such as cycle to cycle variation. On the other hand, the LES generally has an ability to resolve all relevant flow structures and predict cyclic variations but under large increase of computational cost. Aiming to provide an optimum between accuracy and computational cost, in this work PANS

turbulence method coupled with FGM tabulated chemistry approach was employed to predict CCV of the DF engine. Experimentally measured cyclic pressure variations for the engine used in this study are not available. In order to perform a numerical study initial and boundary conditions were perturbed based on the work presented in [16, 19, 36] where detailed investigation of CCV of dual fuel engine similar in size to the engine utilized in this work is performed. Parameters that were varied from the nominal values are initial pressure and temperature, start of injection, amount of injected diesel fuel and mass fraction of premixed methane. This test is mainly performed to investigate feasibility of FGM PANS methodology to predict CCV for DF configuration with respect to accuracy and computational time. Usually, multi-cycle engine simulations are performed by running several sequential full engine cycles. In this study, thirty single cycles were simulated in parallel on a 90-degree sector mesh which enables additional reduction in computational time. In addition, several single cycle simulations can be used to numerically identify the most influential parameters leading to the CCV and hence provide guidance for engine design and consequently enable reduction of hardware iterations and testing. The outcome of engine multi-cycle simulation is shown in Figure 13. In [3] it has been reported that CCV in the output of DF engine at the light load with very lean mixtures, such in this case, needs to be kept well below a value of 5-10%. In the presented numerical study pressure values varied $\pm 12\%$ from the average pressure value. It is evident from Figure 14 that numerically obtained pressure traces averaged over 30 cycle is in good agreement with the average pressure from the measurement. For the comparison of the required computational time the same operating point was additionally calculated with GGPR approach for combustion modelling coupled with PANS turbulence model. In Table 2 computational time required for the simulation of single and multiple cycles of dual fuel combustion process utilizing different numerical approaches is shown. The FGM table has to be generated only once prior to the CFD simulation and then the same table is used for every cycle. GGPR PANS and GGPR LES simulations were run only for one engine cycle,

FIGURE 13 Cycle to cycle pressure variations as predicted by PANS simulation

FIGURE 14 Averaged pressure trace obtained FGM PANS simulation compared to the one cycle GGPR PANS simulation and averaged measured pressure

TABLE 2 Comparison of computational time required for the simulation of DF combustion process utilizing different numerical approaches

	FGM PANS medium mesh	GGPR PANS medium mesh	GGPR LES fine mesh
Table generation	1h 30 min	/	/
Solver per case	5h 24 min	8h 48 min	52h 30 min
Solver for 30 cases	162h	265h	1575h

time for the multi-cycle simulation is approximated. It is evident that employing FGM for combustion modelling and PANS for turbulence modelling enables substantial reduction in computational time.

Figures 15 and 16 show the outcome of the FGM PANS simulation on the medium mesh for engine operating points

FIGURE 15 Pressure trace as predicted by FGM PANS for the middle injection engine operating point in comparison to the measurement

FIGURE 16 Pressure trace as predicted by FGM PANS for the middle injection engine operating point in comparison to the measurement

with middle and late injection. For these two cases only the first cycle of FGM PANS simulation is compared to the measurement. In both cases numerical results showed a small offset in the ignition delay time and slightly overpredicted peak pressure values.

Figure 17 provides comparison of the rate of heat release (RoHR) as predicted by FGM PANS approach on the medium mesh for three engine operating points. The operating points are referred to as early (simple dashed line), medium (solid line) and late (dashed-dotted line) depending on their injection timing. Presented RoHR curves illustrate the influence of injection timing on the combustion process at very small diesel fractions. As the injection timing is shifted to later crank angles, a premixed combustion peak, most likely caused by diesel autoignition, becomes more significant. In the case of late injection timing, start of the combustion is significantly delayed and the flame propagation through the mixture of natural gas and air is slow. In case of medium injection timing, combustion starts at an approximately same crank angle as

FIGURE 17 Rate of heat release as predicted by FGM PANS for three engine operating points

in the case of early injection timing. Compared to the late injection combustion phasing happens earlier, combustion process is faster and higher values of the RoHR are obtained. At the early injection timing, combustion phasing is delayed and the main ascent in the RoHR curve develops later compared to medium injection timing. However, combustion process is fast and the highest values of the RoHR are obtained in the case of early injection.

Summary/Conclusions

This paper presented a 3D-CFD simulation methodology for more cost-effective development of diesel ignited gas engine. A substantial reduction in computational time was obtained by coupling FGM based tabulated chemistry approach for dual fuel combustion with PANS $k-\epsilon-\zeta-f$ SSV model for turbulence. The validation of proposed methodology was carried out utilizing available measurements of dual fuel combustion process obtained from a single cylinder research engine. In order to test feasibility of the FGM PANS methodology single and multiple cycle simulations for three different engine operating points were performed and compared to the numerical results obtained from detailed chemistry calculation coupled with LES turbulence modelling approach and available measurements. The TU Wien mechanism which considers 75 chemical species, and 344 elementary reactions was employed to represent reaction chemistry. Comparison of the computational times showed that employing FGM PANS approach offers a speed-up of approximately 10 times compared to GGPR LES simulation for single cycle on a given mesh. The same reduction in computational time is obtained for multiple cycle simulation – roughly 10 times for 30 engine cycles. The proposed FGM PANS methodology showed ability to accurately predict measured pressure traces for all tested engine operating points. In addition, employing the PANS modeling approach for turbulence enabled capturing unsteady flow features more accurately compared to the conventional RANS with less computational cells than needed for LES. Moreover, the FGM PANS methodology showed potential to predict engine cycle to cycle variations once more proving its advantage over the RANS approach. The overall conclusion that can be drawn from this work is that FGM PANS methodology provides accurate results with affordable computational cost.

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Definitions/Abbreviations

3D-CFD - 3 Dimensional – Computational Fluid Dynamics

CA - Crank angle

CCV - Cycle to cycle variation

DF - Dual fuel

DFICE - Dual fuel internal combustion engine

DNS - Direct numerical simulation

FGM - Flamelet Generated Manifold

GGPR - General Gas Phase Reaction

ICE - Internal combustion engine

LEC - Large Engine Competence Center

LES - Large Eddy Simulation

PANS - Partially-Averaged Navier-Stokes

PSR - Perfectly Stirred Reactor

RANS - Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes

SSV - Scale Supplying Variable